

Influence of Job Satisfaction as Correlates of Employee Performance for Effective Services Delivery among Library Staff in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

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Abstract

Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this study was to explore the influence of job satisfaction on employees' performance for effective service delivery among library staff in Usmanu Danfodiyo University with 3 research objectives and was used in formulating research questions, and 1 null hypothesis.

Methodology: The study's design was correlational survey research. The population was 123 library staff. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Data obtained from the questionnaire was analyzed using frequency, mean, and standard deviation at an accepted average mean of 2.50 and simple linear regression analysis with a 0.05 level of significance using SPSS version 25.

Findings: The findings of the study revealed that reasonable salary package, timely promotion and career development have a significant influence on job satisfaction, and the Pearson correlation indicated that there is a significant positive correlation between job satisfaction and employees' performance at UDUS library staff with ($r=.648$, and $p\text{-value}=.000$ which is $p<0.05$).

Recommendation and Conclusion: The researchers recommended, among other things, that employers always consider the salary and welfare of their employees, university management should not hesitate to promote punctual staff members who are due for promotion, and Career development such as attending seminars, conferences, and workshops will motivate library personnel and enable them to improve their skills for effective service delivery. The researchers concluded that job satisfaction is a critical predictor of employees' performance, and the library should prioritize strategies to enhance job satisfaction so as to improve performance outcomes.

Study Type: Research paper

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Employees' Performance, Effective Service Delivery, Library Staff, University

Introduction

Librarians are information organisers and disseminators of various types of information with the aim of responding to the information needs of the users. Employees such as librarians, among other professionals, are the most valuable strategic resources and assets for organizations. Employee job satisfaction needs to be assessed in order to achieve user or customer satisfaction (Siswanto & Yuliana, 2022). It is obvious that librarians, particularly in an academic environment, render free-based services to users to support teaching, learning, and research in the community they are serving. Consequently, their sole source of income is the salary they receive from their employers. In this case, one of the terms of service and a requirement for attending to employees' demands is reasonable payment, which is a

component or measure of job satisfaction. In other words, one of the most important elements in creating a psychological contract between an employer and an employee is remuneration. Okolocha (2021) defines a salary as a sum of money paid to an employee in exchange for labour that is completed. He argued that an employee's pay establishes a psychological contract with their employer and that when the company or an organization breaches that contract, the employee is required to feel dissatisfied. Employees' performance will also be affected when they are dissatisfied with the payment. Salary is one of the major factors that influences job satisfaction. However, it is not the only factor; attending conferences and workshops to acquire skills, timely promotion, and career advancement are also essential for maintaining high-performance levels by employees (Ilkoz, 2024).

In a general overview, many scholars argued that there is a significant correlation between job satisfaction and employee performance, which could lead to effective service delivery in an organization. Inuwa (2016) found that job satisfaction had a positive impact on employee performance. So also, in the library settings, job satisfaction or dissatisfaction as a result of salary earned, promotion or career development by the librarians have a significant correlation with their performance, which could positively or negatively affect the effectiveness of the services offered to the library users, with a similar perspective stating that it's important to know that work attitude and the job performance of employees in any organization are vital not only for the growth of the organization but also for the growth of individual employees (Oyeniran & Irenoa, 2021). Sambo (2014) claims that librarians' degree of job satisfaction influences the calibre of services they offer. Moreover, Memon et al. (2023) asserted that job satisfaction and employee performance are essential tools for enhancing organizational performance over time in order to accomplish strategic objectives.

Satisfaction, according to the Oxford Lexico Online Dictionary (2022), means the fulfilment of one's wishes, expectations, needs, or pleasure. Konappa (2014) posited that satisfaction refers to the feeling of being pleased with results. Satisfaction can be explained as the accomplishment of self-desire or self-need and the happiness obtained after the achievement. Job satisfaction was identified as the level of contentment of an employee about one's job experience. Job satisfaction, according to Arshad, Arshad and Zakaria (2023), is an organization's unnoticed success, which refers to a collection of positive feelings that employees have about their jobs. Shahzad, Khan, and Shabbir (2023) cited McShane as viewed job satisfaction as employees' expectations for benefits from the job.

Employees' performance is a result of the employee's satisfaction with the job. Employee performance, according to Darvishmotevali and Ali (2020), is an indicator of how well an employee can carry out his tasks and obligations. Werdhiastutie, Suhariadi, and Partiw (2020) stated that employee performance is one of the most crucial factors in achieving organizational goals. Employees who are productive and efficient can help an organisation boost productivity and the quality of services provided, as well as increase employee and user satisfaction (Nadya, Ameer, & Zaamil, 2022; Rahmah, Rouns, & Luck, 2022). For the attainment of employee performance, especially within the university library workforce, and in order to provide effective service delivery, employees' needs should be addressed.

Statement of Problem

Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in enhancing employee performance and overall organizational effectiveness. Librarians who are satisfied with their jobs tend to exhibit higher levels of motivation and engagement. Factors that influence job satisfaction by librarians for effective service delivery according to the literature include but are not limited to competitive salary package, promotion, teamwork, conducive environment, incentives, supervision, co-workers, educational qualification, contingent benefits and career development etc. (Nilasari, et al., 2024; Okrah, Adjei, & Korang, 2024; Aliyu, 2023; Momon, et al. 2023; Ahmed, Mohammed, & Daudu, 2021; Nagaraju, 2017; & Inuwa, 2016).

However, despite these important roles of librarians in delivering effective and efficient services to the library users for academic excellent, some librarians, particularly in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS) Library, still exhibit poor attitudes towards their work and those they serve (users). Could it be a result of a lack of a motivational salary package? Could it be due to a lack of promotion? Or due to inadequate career development? Or due to the lack of proper supervision? The study tested the hypotheses above to find out whether there was a significant correlation between job satisfaction and employee performance among librarians of UDUS Library since there is no research conducted in the area to the best knowledge of the researchers at this time with the aim of bridging the research gap.

Research Questions

1. What are the factors that influence library staff satisfaction with their jobs in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University Library?
2. How does job satisfaction influence employees' performance in terms of effective service delivery among library staff in the UDUS library?
3. What are the strategies for enhancing employees' performance of library staff for effective service delivery in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Library?

Hypothesis

The researchers used the null hypothesis (H_0) to test whether there is a significant correlation between the variables at a significance level of 0.05

H_{01} : There is no significant correlation between job satisfaction and employees' performance for effective service delivery of library staff in the UDUS library

Review of Related Empirical Literature

A study on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance was carried out by Udem and Bassey (2024) in Federal University Libraries in southeast Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study, and three hypotheses were examined at a significance level of 0.05. The study used a correlational research design. Academic librarians and library staff from the five federal university libraries in South-East Nigeria were among the 299 library employees that made up the population. Data was gathered using a structured questionnaire. The reliability of the instruments was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Research problems were addressed, and hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). The findings of the study showed that there was a moderate positive relationship between job satisfaction and the job performance of library staff. There was a moderate positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance of male library staff but a weak positive relationship among the female library staff. A moderate positive relationship between job satisfaction and the job performance of academic librarians and a weak positive relationship between job satisfaction and the job performance of library officers were also observed. Based on the findings, the implications of the study were pointed out; among them is that it was recommended that the library management should develop a policy that will increase and sustain the job satisfaction of the personnel by providing a conducive work environment and recognition of inputs of the workforce.

Memon et al. (2023) conducted a study on the Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Construction Industry of Pakistan. Multiple regression analysis was used for statistical analysis of the study's population of 85, which was gathered through a questionnaire survey as part of the data-gathering process. According to the results, all of the models have a high ability to compute the increase in employee performance criteria via the predicting variables. The overall models are significant because a value less than 0.05 indicates that they are significant. The study's findings

assist practitioners in understanding the critical criteria that will increase employer satisfaction and improve performance.

An empirical study on the effect of salary on employee productivity was carried out by Nagaraju (2017) in Karnataka, India's public and private sector banks. There were 150 participants in the study (92 from state banks and 58 from private banks). For the purpose of gathering data, a simple random sampling technique was employed to choose respondents from each bank. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire. Analysis of variance (ANOVA), mean score, and standard deviation were used to analyze the data. The findings of the study revealed that salary and promotion, among others, have a significant impact on employees' performance.

Similarly, Inuwa (2016) embarked on a study on employee performance and job satisfaction among Bauchi State University, Gadau's non-academic staff. The researcher distributed 270 questionnaires to the respondents using systematic random sampling, and the return rate was 256. The data was analyzed using multiple regression with the aid of SPSS. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of the university's non-academic staff.

Aliyu (2023) conducted a study on the Work Environment and Job Performance of Librarians at Bayero University, Kano (BUK) Library. The researcher adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 111 librarians from the BUK library. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire and was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings of the study revealed that the job performance of librarians in the BUK library is high as a result of teamwork and a conducive environment. The researcher recommended, among others, that university management should provide a conducive environment to the librarians.

Ahmed, Mohammed and Daudu (2021) embarked on a research titled Effect of Motivation on Job Performance of Librarians in Academic Libraries in Gombe State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research was adopted with a sample of 63 librarians in academic libraries in Gombe state. The instrument used was a questionnaire, and out of 63 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 57 copies were returned and were used for data analysis. The method of data analysis was descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that the training of librarians and monetary factors (salaries, bonuses and incentives) were the factors that motivated the performance of the librarians. They recommended that management should endeavour to improve the well-being of librarians to enhance their job performance.

In a similar vein, Okrah, Adjei and Korang (2024) conducted a correlational survey research on the Effect of Job Satisfaction on employee performance at Berekum College of Education, Ghana. The study was based on 129 respondents and analyzed using multiple linear regression. It was revealed that among all the nine variables used in examining job satisfaction, only the nature of work significantly positively affects employees' performance. The remaining eight variables, such as salaries, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent benefits, co-workers, communication, and operating procedures, did not significantly affect employees' performance. Finally, gender, age, and education were established to have a significant effect on employees' performance. The study concludes that the major determinants of improved employee performance are the nature of work, gender, age, and education.

Nilasari et al. (2024) in their study on the Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance of Educational Staff. The researchers used a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 24 educational staff from the faculty of economics and business at the University of Trisukti, Indonesia. Because the population is relatively small, a saturated/census sample is used with Smart-PLS software for data analysis. The research established that there is job satisfaction for educational staff, which comes from co-workers, supervision, pay, promotion opportunities, etc. They recommended that managers should update regulations regarding job promotions and set clear promotion periods. Then,

promotional policies should be socialized so that all educational staff can understand them clearly. Managers are also expected to act fairly in providing promotional opportunities to all education staff.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational survey research design. According to Mole (2019), it is the type of design which seeks to establish the nature, magnitude and direction of the relationship between two or more variables (i.e. what relationship exists, the extent it exists and the manner it exists). The purpose of such surveys is to determine the extent to which the unknown status of one variable can be predicted from the known status of another variable. The population of the study was 123 library staff of the Abdullahi Fodiyo Library Complex, UDUS. The population is manageable and does not require sampling. A probability sampling technique using proportionate stratified sampling was used. The population of library attendants was 60, library officers 46, and academic librarians 17, respectively. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire that was distributed to one hundred and twenty-three (123) library staff. Frequency, mean and standard deviation, using 4 rating scale: Strongly Agree; 3.50-4.00, Agree; 2.50-3.49, Disagree; 1.50-2.49 and Strongly Disagree; 0.50-1.49 and the accepted average mean is 2.50 was employed for data analysis. A simple linear regression analysis with a 0.05 level of significance was used to test the null hypothesis. Any score that is greater than the p-value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is considered accepted. However, for any score that is less than the p-value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the factors that influence library staff satisfaction with their jobs in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Library?

Table 1: Mean responses of the respondents on the factors that influence library staff satisfaction with their jobs in the UDUS Library

S/N	Item statements	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	S.D	R
1	Reasonable salary package	52	68	3	0	3.40	.53	A
2	Timely promotion	46	68	8	1	3.29	.62	A
3	Career development	40	74	7	2	3.24	.62	A
4	Team-work	40	57	14	12	3.02	.91	A
5	Conducive environment	44	56	22	1	3.16	.74	A
6	Incentives	55	56	11	1	3.34	.67	A
7	Annual bonus	66	44	12	1	3.42	.70	A
8	Supervision	0	0	44	79	1.36	.48	D
9	Co-workers	0	22	56	45	1.81	.71	D
10	Contingent benefits	56	55	11	1	3.35	.67	A
11	Operating procedures	11	11	44	57	1.80	.93	D
12	Educational Qualification	66	33	12	12	3.24	.98	A
13	Timely payment	67	33	22	1	3.35	.79	A
	Cluster Mean					2.90	.71	A

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree and SD= Strongly Disagree

The result of the study, as presented in Table 1, shows the factors that influence UDUS library staff satisfaction with their jobs. The result indicates that reasonable salary package, timely promotion and career development, and teamwork, among others, have a significant influence on the job satisfaction of UDUS library staff, with the agreed mean and standard deviation ranging between 3.02 – 3.42 and

SD= .53 – .98 respectively on the 10 items. While supervision, co-workers and operational procedures fall below the average mean (2.50) and are therefore rejected. However, the cluster mean of 2.90 shows a significant influence as well. This is in line with the findings of Udem and Bassey (2024) and Okrah, Adjei, & Korang (2024), who surveyed Job Satisfaction as a Correlate of Job Performance of Library Staff in Federal University Libraries in Southeast Nigeria. The findings stated that there was a moderate positive relationship between job satisfaction and the job performance of library staff.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of job satisfaction on employees’ performance for effective service delivery among library staff in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Library?

Table 2: Mean responses of the respondents on the influence of job satisfaction on employees’ performance for effective service delivery among library staff in UDUS Library

S/N	Item statements	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	S.D	R
1	As a result of the reasonable salary package, employees are less likely to seek employment elsewhere, which enables the library to maintain its workforce for effective service delivery	59	56	7	1	3.41	.63	A
2	Timely promotion motivates library staff to be more enthusiastic and engaged in their work, which translates into better service for library users	51	61	10	1	3.32	.65	A
3	Career development makes library staff acquire knowledge and develop more skills in order to render quality services to the users	44	72	6	1	3.29	.59	A
4	Teamwork fosters trust, communication, and a sense of belonging among team members, which leads to problem-solving and innovation	46	53	12	12	3.08	.92	A
5	A safe and comfortable place would lead to high-quality work	45	55	23	0	3.18	.72	A
6	Financial incentives motivate employees to exceed their employer’s expectations	56	55	12	0	3.36	.65	A
7	Annual bonuses boost the morale of employees in discharging their duties	67	44	11	1	3.44	.69	A
8	Proper supervision makes employees to be punctual	1	0	46	76	1.40	.53	D
9	Co-workers enable employers to reduce counterproductive behaviour	0	21	55	47	1.79	.71	D
10	Contingent benefits lead to improved performance levels when employees perceive the rewards are valuable and attainable	56	55	12	0	3.36	.65	A
11	Operating procedures provide guidelines and enhance work discipline to execute tasks efficiently	11	11	46	55	1.82	.93	D
12	Employees with high qualifications often generate innovative ideas and demonstrate better problem-solving skills	68	33	12	10	3.29	.94	A

13	Prompt payment boosts the morale of employees, leading to improved productivity	64	37	22	0	3.34	.76	A
Cluster Mean						2.92	.72	A

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree and SD= Strongly Disagree

The result of the study, as presented in Table 2, shows the influence of job satisfaction on employees’ performance for effective service delivery among UDUS library staff. The result shows that as a result of the reasonable salary package, employees are less likely to seek employment elsewhere, which enables the library to maintain its workforce for effective service delivery; timely promotion motivates library staff to be more enthusiastic and engaged in their work which translates into better service for library users, career development makes library staff to acquire knowledge and develop more skills in order to render quality services to the users, Teamwork fosters trust, communication, and a sense of belonging among team members, which would lead to problem-solving and innovation among others with the agreed mean and standard deviation ranging between 3.08 – 3.44 and SD= .59 – .94 respectively on the 10 items. The remaining 3 items, such as supervision, co-workers and operating procedures, fall below the average mean (2.50) and are therefore rejected. Nonetheless, the cluster mean of 2.92 also shows a significant influence as well. This corroborates with the findings of Aliyu (2023) and Nagaraju (2017), who found that salary and promotion, among others, have a significant impact on employees’ performance.

Hypothesis: There is no significant correlation between job satisfaction and employees’ performance for effective service delivery of library staff in the UDUS library

Table 3: Regression analysis on the correlation between job satisfaction and employees’ performance for effective service delivery of library staff in the UDUS library

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	R	P-value
Job Satisfaction	123	2.90	.39			
Employees’ Performance	123	2.92	.37	121	.648	.000

r=.779, p-value= .000

The result presented in Table 3 indicates a correlation between job satisfaction and employees’ performance for effective service delivery among UDUS library staff. The correlation was found to be significant with (r= .648, Df= 121, p-value .000, p<0.05). This implies that there is a significant positive correlation between job satisfaction and employees’ performance in terms of effective service delivery among UDUS library staff. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This is in tandem with Memon et al. (2023), who found that there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance in the construction industry of Pakistan with a 0.01 level of significance.

Research Question 4: What are the strategies for enhancing employee performance of library staff for effective service delivery in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Library?

Table 4: Mean responses of the respondents on the strategies for enhancing employee performance of library staff for effective service delivery in UDUS Library

S/N	Item statements	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	S.D	R
1	Reasonable salary package	59	52	11	1	3.37	.68	A
2	Timely promotion	58	54	8	3	3.36	.71	A
3	Career development	52	58	10	3	3.29	.72	A
4	Staff commendation letter	53	59	6	5	3.30	.74	A
5	Team-work	23	54	41	5	2.77	.79	A
6	Conducive environment	36	49	23	15	2.86	.97	A
7	Incentives	32	47	21	23	2.72	.87	A
8	Annual bonus	36	56	32	9	2.80	.85	A
9	Contingent benefits	27	53	30	13	2.76	.91	A
10	Educational Qualification	26	45	31	21	2.62	1.0	A
	Cluster Mean					2.98	.82	A

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree and SD= Strongly Disagree

The result of the study, as presented in Table 4, shows the strategies for enhancing employees' performance of library staff for effective service delivery in UDUS library. The result shows that reasonable salary package, timely promotion, career development, teamwork, conducive environment, staff commendation letter etc. are the major strategies for enhancing employees' performance with above average mean (2.50) and standard deviation ranging between 3.37 – 2.62 and SD= .68 – 1.0 respectively on the 10 items. The cluster mean of 2.98 shows agreement on the above strategies. The findings are in tandem with Aliyu (2023) and Rachman (2021), who found that comfort, incentives, pay, working conditions, etc., improve the performance of the employees.

Summary of Major Findings

1. The researchers found out that reasonable salary package, timely promotion career development, teamwork, incentives, annual bonus etc. were the factors influencing job satisfaction of UDUS library staff
2. It was revealed that job satisfaction has a significant influence on employees' performance for effective service delivery among UDUS library staff
3. The Pearson correlation coefficient indicated that there is a significant correlation between job satisfaction and employees' performance for effective service delivery among UDUS library staff
4. The study also found that reasonable salary packages, timely promotion, career development staff commendation letters, and teamwork, among others, were among the strategies for enhancing employees' performance for effective service delivery

Recommendation

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations were made to the relevant stakeholders. If implemented, they will enhance employees' performance and lead to effective service delivery by the UDUS library staff.

1. Employers should always consider the salary and welfare of their employees for effective service delivery
2. University management should not hesitate to promote punctual staff members who are due for promotion

3. Career development such as attending seminars, conferences, and workshops will motivate the library personnel and enable them to improve their skills for effective service delivery
4. University management should always commend the effort of its staff for a job well done
5. Management should establish teamwork in solving organizational problems. This would also bring innovations that improve library staff productivity.
6. Management should endeavour to provide a conducive environment for high-quality work by the library staff
7. The government should always make employee welfare a top priority. This would motivate employees to exceed their employer's expectations in terms of quality service delivery
8. University management should endeavour to send its employees to acquire additional qualifications. This would enable them to generate innovative ideas and demonstrate better problem-solving skills

Conclusion

This study has empirically established a significant positive correlation between job satisfaction and employee performance. According to the findings, job satisfaction is a key indicator of employee performance. The findings indicate that higher levels of job satisfaction are positively correlated with improved employee performance, leading to more effective and efficient service delivery. This underscores the importance of fostering a supportive and fulfilling work environment to enhance overall productivity and service quality. By addressing factors that contribute to job satisfaction, such as recognition, professional development, and work-life balance, the university can ensure that its library staff remain motivated and committed to delivering exceptional services.

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